

“But What is Home?”: Exploring Diasporic Imagination and Identity Relations in M.G. Vassanji’s *Uhuru Street*

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Abstract

Having positioned himself in the “beyond”, M.G. Vassanji’s diasporic self, in his collection of short stories Uhuru Street, visits and revisits the double migration of Indians settled in the Uhuru Street of the city of Dar es Salaam on the east coast of Africa. The story cycle implicates the highly stratified tripartite society - which includes Indians, Africans and Arabs - within the folds of immense socio-political tensions that transform these communities over the course of pre-independence and independent Tanzania. The history of the dislocation of diasporic Indians is foregrounded by essentializing the cross-cultural transactions and complex identity relations engendered by the strategic importance of the Indian Ocean that problematizes any static notion of belonging. Thus, this paper attempts to analyse the corresponding themes of transnationalism, cosmopolitanism and universalism which come to permeate the socio-cultural lives of the people of Uhuru Street as their hybrid, interstitial identities resist any monolithic categorisation. As the Shamsis - a hybrid, minor community - is fictionalised by Vassanji to navigate the possibilities of belonging and de-categorizations, his story cycle reinforces the in-betweenness of identities that corresponds closely to a cosmopolitan turn of a globalised world that imagines permanence in constant flux and movement(s). However, the paper also seeks to expose the gaps within this perpetual discontinuity in belonging to come together as a community due to socio-economic and racial differentiation that inhabits this landscape as sub-categorisations. While the already syncretic immigrants from Uhuru Street aspire to make the world their homeland, their collective experience of migrancy post-independence draws another critical attention to the question of diasporic imagination - what can the new configurations of transnational spaces offer to these fluid identities?

Keywords: Migration, Diaspora, Belonging, Identity, Transculturation, Africa

The writer must write if only to recreate that lost world — for whatever reason — which soon exists nowhere but in his memory.

– M. G. Vassanji (1997, p.15)

In his essay “Negotiating Caribbean Identities”, Stuart Hall comments how Caribbean diaspora engenders the first unique example of a purest diaspora (1995, p. 6) where cultural identities are characterised by complex processes of negotiation and transculturation. While the diasporic imagination(s) now travels far to the limits of the Atlantic Ocean, and also the Pacific Ocean, in exploring the subjectivities informed by the relationship between the sense of self and place, the idiosyncratic cultural negotiations, diverse economic transactions and transregional exchange networks that the commercial and historical abundance of the Indian Ocean have brought to the world are lately been recognized by the diaspora and migration studies. M.G. Vassanji (1950 -)'s voice has thus grown exponentially in observing the negotiations involving the challenges and changes of displacement affecting the Africans of Indian descent across the Indian Ocean world. In his short story cycle, *Uhuru Street* (1992), the writer fictionalises the lives of the Shamsis - members of the minority Ismaili community with hybrid identities from Dar es Salaam, the largest city in East Africa, Tanzania - to contextualise the significant political and cultural changes in the history of Tanzania between the 50s and the 80s. For Vassanji, the setting is both a physical and imaginative construct, a meditation on the colonised past and the new possibilities of (un)belonging which opened after Independence. The writer traces the double migration of the Indian Muslim community (Shamsis), firstly, to East Africa in the late nineteenth century as “humble street traders middling skilled artisans and affluent merchant families such as the Karimjees” (Brennan & Burton, 2007, p. 35), and later in the 1960s as new immigrants towards Europe and North America. As the arrival of Indians marked a socioeconomic and racial stratification of the place within the African, Arab and European communities (Brennan & Burton, 2007, p. 52), the Africanization of postcolonial Tanzania complicated the questions of identity relations and belonging for the Indian communities.

“Belonging is not a privilege given to you, it is not a choice you make; it is a feeling inside you” (2016, p. 32), believes M.S. Vassanji whose own diasporic consciousness enables him to approach the dislocation of Indians in the Indian Ocean world from “the beyond” (Bhabha, 1994, p. 1). Embodying identity as a “palimpsest” (1997, p. 17), Vassanji’s characters thus inhabit interstitial, liminal, and in-between worlds by navigating the processes of transcultural dealings and “crossing identity thresholds, such as the ones built around the secularreligious, Western-Eastern, and present-past divide” (Ortega, 2021, p. 1). As migrancy destabilised the dominant narrative of a destined home incorporating a monolithic identity, the opening of new possibilities of belonging within the framework of cosmopolitanism, transnationalism and globalisation emerged as fluid spaces to embrace the hybrid identities within a fragmented society. It is, in fact, no coincidence that the genre of short story cycle,

which itself borders between novels and short stories, is chosen as a metaphor for the in-transit subject positions which simultaneously “demonstrates the strong collective impulse that has characterised much ethnic fiction” (Davis, 1999, p. 24). The street is described from shifting narratorial positions over diverse subjects such that the narrative accounts for both an individual’s private life and his interactions with his family and other communities at large, through objective and subjective positions. The stories are evocatively foregrounded by the grand metanarratives of history such as the First World War, Independence, Socialist reforms in Tanzania, the visit of Queen Margaret to Dar es Salaam, or the Ugandan Asians exodus, while communities are formed only superficially given the force of historical, political, economic and cultural tensions ultimately subsume the uniting principle of the place. However, stories are drawn from familial bonds extending to friendship(s), to belonging to the same town, ethnicity, class, or gender, and so can be “said to constitute the central character of a cycle” (Ingram, 1997, p. 22), even if the individual is at variance with his own social community, or shares merely a relationship of dependence with them. Nevertheless, transgressing boundaries is deterred and any assumptions of life are governed by codes so that the community’s pride and purity is maintained. In this story cycle, Uhuru Street hence emerges as a stage that “provides narratives and comments on its own history” (Bardolph, 1995, p. 85).

The thematic developments of the stories in *Uhuru Street* span over generations where a strong nostalgia for past opposes an “ambivalent affiliation” (Malak, 1993, p. 280) of the diasporic consciousness. The underlying cultural and racial differentiations in a hierarchical, tripartite Tanzanian society propel these longings, which I argue, have to be contextualised in the background of intra-community exchanges, inter-racial/inter-community relations, and emigration. Not only Indian customs, social traditions, food and world-views come to define the lives of Tanzanian Indians, their collective identity is thwarted by class, family genealogies or native village. As a result, we see how in the first story “In the Quiet of a Sunday Afternoon”, the narrator’s father-in-law, German after making an intimidating investigation about her Indian pedigree, declares Zarina’s family “third class” (Vassanji, 1992, p. 7):

‘I knew your father,’ he said when he returned. ‘What town was he from?’
‘Mbinga,’ she answered. ‘I know that! Where in India?’
‘I don’t know. In Cutch or Gujarat somewhere.’
‘Mudra,’ he said, nodding at me. ‘I remember when he came to Africa.’
She said nothing. (Vassanji, 1992, p. 6)

For German, socio-economic status is the only signifier of social respectability which marginalises the likes of Roshan Mattress, a woman notorious “for her free ways” (Vassanji, 1992, p. 10), and also the narrator, “an orphan half-caste...mother black. [I was] brought up by an Indian family, half servant and half son” (Vassanji, 1992, p. 9) who’s infamously given the only identity - “Black” (Vassanji, 1992, p. 9). Similarly, in “The Relief from Drill”, the

narrator's brother, Aloo tries to betray their modest status by pretending to buy cheap from the mnada, the open-air African market, from his mother's meagre savings. The social space already segregated by linguistic, ethnic, religious and economic differences were not to be crossed by frequenting the Mnada street market, where jobless Africans were stereotyped to inhabit a socially denigrated ways of thievery and criminality (Vassanji, 1992, p. 44). This discourse of segregation had also permeated the faultlines of ethnicity within the South Asian communities such that every subgroup internalised the loyalty to their own boundaries: "the Pereras were Goans and their affairs of little interest to the rest of us" (Vassanji, 1992, p. 20). In the story "Alzira", when Tembombili, "one of Dar's several crazies, a small, thin, Goan man," (Vassanji, 1992, p. 27) is almost beaten up the mob before being rescued by Alzira's brother, Pius, the contrasting reactions of the boy narrator and Alzira reinforce the ethnic divide operating within a seemingly single community. A community depending heavily on the idea of *kismet*, "birth, marriage, and death were preordained, as [Mother] often said. You had many choices in life: but not with these three" (Vassanji, 1992, p. 25-26), the hierarchy within the South Asian communal cocoon found a way to survive against any determining 'pollutant'.

Interracial relationships, another recurring theme in which the action transpires, form a major dynamic of Uhuru Street. There's an ironic ridicule of diverse identities in Tanzania whose psychological and intellectual growth are stunted by the prevalent racism and discrimination. "For a Shilling" describes Uhuru Street as "the crazy world of our daily associations-of Arabs, Africans, Asians and assorted halfcastes..." (Vassanji, 1992, p. 35), which problematizes the privileges and cross-cultural negotiations marking the space of social interactions. While the colonised past still have South Asian communities mimicking their "superiors", as in the story "Alzira" where the narrator's mother looked for cultural affirmations from the Europeans: "Any European woman who chanced by on our street was the subject of Mother's deepest scrutiny, as she watched out for new patterns" (Vassanji, 1992, p. 25), on the other hand, the fear of losing one's values and turning into one of 'them' in Post-Independence Tanzania is articulated by the resistant mother in "Leaving", who warns her son, Aloo who's departing to North America for higher education, against marrying a white woman (Vassanji, 1992, p. 68). As Indians continued to be stigmatised as 'uncivil' and incapable, the story "English Lessons" emphasises on the remnants of imperialism through the assistant headmaster, Mr. Stuart whose own origins were in question:

Stuart's mission in school was to civilise. Two months before, the class had been instructed on the use of the 'English-style' toilets. This, after he discovered a 'mess' on the lavatory floor. 'Do you think the bowl is there to wash your faces in, you numbskulls?' And then, grinning like a mischievous dog, he revealed a happy discovery: 'And tell your other teachers the seat is not to be mounted either!' The 'other teachers' were Indians. (Vassanji, 1992, pp. 56 - 57)

The oppositional framework which the Africans and Indians occupy in Tanzania bears heavily on this short story cycle. The second story “Ali”, recounts the plight of Africans during colonial times whose existence were exclusively defined through their requisite skills and labour which were exploited to privilege Others. Ali who fulfilled the societal expectations drawn for him, however, was dismissed for aspiring more when upon being caught peeping at the narrator’s sister, Mehroon while taking her afternoon bath, he expressed his wish to marry her (Vassanji, 1992, p. 19). The attempt to blur interracial divide is thus unimaginable as Vassanji illustrates through a vivid description of intercommunity conflicts in another story “The Driver,” in which the African driver, Idi, gives a glimpse of daily scuffles between the Africans and the Arabs in Tanzania which “almost always end [ed] at the brink of bloodshed” (Vassanji, 1992, p. 53). The constant friction and racist stereotypes are also well brought out in the “The Sounds of the Night” when the boy narrator defends his race against the devaluation of their cultural beliefs and practices:

‘Where are you going to, child?’ he said.

‘To the mosque.’

‘The Indian mosque. What do you do there?’

‘We pray.’

‘You don’t pray, you make fun!’ He started mocking. ‘Ai-yai-yai-nyai,’ he sang in a high-pitched voice.

Partisanship got the better of me and in a rage I cried, ‘We don’t make fun! We pray! It is *you* who makes fun!’ (Vassanji, 1992, p. 59)

Post-Independence Tanzania reversed the social roles between the Africans and Indians so much so that the South Asian Communities were pushed to the edge of living. Harboursing a longing for a past replete with priviledges, the story "What Good Times We Had" shows an Indian woman determined to move to Canada, but instead meeting her inevitable fate of brutal rape and murder at the hands of an African banker who avenges the history of racial insult and systemic violence of his race by upthrowing the social dynamics: “And she thought of all the black men she had presided over almost all her thirty-seven years with scorn...Was this revenge, or plain avarice?” (Vassanji, 1992, p. 84). At the same time, the story “Breaking Loose” ventures into new possibilities for inter-racial relations. “The world [is] which was not ready for it-” (Vassanji, 1992, p. 87) witnesses a blooming affair between Yasmin Rajan, an Indian Tanzanian university student, and an African professor of sociology, Daniel Akoto. When their intellect and a search for ethnic authenticity bring them closer, it’s only through Akoto that Yasmin’s identity consciousness discovers its hybrid roots, stifled under the layers of histories and traditions. Thus, she emerges as “a new mutant” (Vassanji, 1992, p. 88), one of the many fluid subject positions that correspond to M.S. Vassanji’s in-between worlds, redefined by cultural mobility and migration in terms of identity relations.

The major shift in the lives of the Indians from Dar es Salaam comes with another wave of migration towards Europe and North America - this time either to “revalidate and accept, or reject, what had been learned at home” (Davis, 1999, p. 20). While there may be some people like the main protagonist from “Refugee” whose arrival in Germany launches him into an “utter, utter loneliness under an alien sky” (Vassanji, 1992, p. 122), there also exists the likes of ‘London-returned’ who were culturally swept away. Vassanji, in the story “The London-returned”, carefully reflects on the different kinds of (un)belonging for the immigrants when despite having displaced himself doubly from London to Toronto in the hope of inhabiting his own “thin and marginal world” (Vassanji, 1992, p. 111), the narrator instead finds his wife Amina slowly turning Toronto into their very own Dar. As the narrator muses on his liminality after his divorce from his wife, his “plain longing for a home, a permanence” (Vassanji, 1992, p. 139) brings him back to Dar es Salaam in the story “All Worlds are Possible Now”, suggesting a cyclical nature to migration. However, this time, the city deludes him - “It looks the same...Or do I imagine, delude myself it is the same?” (Vassanji, 1992, p. 131); his ritual of claiming Uhuru Street now lies betrayed without its people, perhaps fulfilled only in his diasporic imagination. The romantic notion of change and belonging in relation to the first generation Indian migrant subjectivities is further jilted when contrasted with the concept of home conceived by the second and third generation of Indians forming a second Indian diaspora in the Indian Ocean world. When Fahndo asks rather rhetorically, ““Yes. But what is home?”” (Vassanji, 1992, p. 135), he speaks for the second Indian diaspora who are now untethered to their homeland, with their Indianness losing its bearings on their cultural identity. At the same time, when Lateef responds, ““The whole world is our home. It’s a global village”” (Vassanji, 1992, p. 135), he opens the contemporary discourse of cosmopolitanism, universalism and transnationalism as fluid negotiations for the migrancy experiences.

Both Lateef and the narrator-protagonist have left Dar and finally returned. While their liminality signifies the ever-expanding transregional networks across the Indian Ocean world, as migrant subjects their identities come to occupy in-between spaces which problematizes any fixed binaries. Moving away from any historical affiliations of the place with his identity, the last narrator in Vassanji’s *Uhuru Street* ultimately realises the hopeless attempt to seek permanence in the city which is itself constantly changing. His insider-outsider position allows him to revisit the surviving link to a usable past of the city, but at the same time as an immigrant he’s condemned to re-imagine his beginnings wherever he is. Indeed, the open identity of Vassanji’s narrator never ceases to make him an Other, even within his own beloved city of Dar es Salaam.

Author's Bio-note

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